

A New Reagent System for the Analysis of Carbofuran and its Application in Environmental Samples

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A new sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed for the determination of carbofuran at sub ppm level. The method is based on the hydrolysis of carbofuran under alkaline condition to carbofuranphenol and subsequent coupling of the phenol with *p*-anisidine and *N*-chlorosuccinimide in the presence of a catalyst. The method is simple, sensitive and free from the interference of other common pesticides and ions.

Carbofuran [2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-7-benzo(*b*)furanyl-methylcarbamate] also known as Furadan, is an effective, contact and systemic broad spectrum insecticide and acaricide. The wide applicability and high toxicity of carbofuran has resulted in numerous instrumental methods for its determination¹. A few spectrophotometric methods are also reported²⁻⁵. In the present method carbofuran is first hydrolyzed by sodium hydroxide to carbofuranphenol followed by oxidative coupling with *p*-anisidine and *N*-chlorosuccinimide in the presence of a catalytic mixture of sodium nitroprusside and manganese dioxide. The resulting greenish blue dye is estimated spectrophotometrically at 660 nm.

Results and Discussion

The color system shows maximum absorbance at 660 nm. The color system obeys Beer's law over the range 2.5–25 µg of carbofuran per 25 ml of final solution (0.1–1.0 ppm) at 660 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 1.9×10^5 (± 100) $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 0.001 µg cm^{-2} respectively.

For hydrolysis of carbofuran, 2 ml of 1.5 M NaOH solution was found to be satisfactory. After adding NaOH to working standard solution of carbofuran, it was kept for 15 min at room temperature for complete hydrolysis. Similarly, 0.5 ml of 0.5% *p*-anisidine, 1.0 ml of 0.1% *N*-chlorosuccinimide solutions and 0.5 ml of catalytic mixture were sufficient for oxidation coupling and complete color development of the solution. There was no change in the absorbance values within the temperature range 20–30°. The color was found to be stable for about 10 h. Constant absorbance values were obtained within pH 12–13 and no buffer was required to stabilize the color.

The effects of common foreign species and other pesticides on the determination of carbofuran were studied. Known amounts of foreign species and pesticides were added to a standard solution containing 5 µg of carbofuran in 25 ml of final solution, prior to hydrolysis. Then these solutions were analyzed by the proposed method. Naphthols and phenols if present interfere with the color reaction. Their interference were removed by washing the

chloroform extract twice with 0.2–0.4 M NaOH solution and then with water to remove these contaminants. At least 1.5 M NaOH was needed for the hydrolysis of carbofuran pesticide. The carbofuran pesticide was not lost during the removal of naphthols and phenols. Tolerance limits (µg/25 ml) of some ions and pesticides are as follows : ethanol (10000), methanol (8700), formaldehyde (7500), DDT and BHC (1000), ethyl parathion (875), dimethoate and phorate (750), ethion (625), Cu^{II} and Co^{II} (500), Pb^{II} and sulphate (450), Zn^{II} (375), bromide and fluoride (250), nitrophenol and cresol (150).

Precision of the method was checked by analysing 5 µg of carbofuran in 25 ml of final solution over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation of absorbance values were found to be ± 0.006 and 3.6% respectively.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss (CZSL-2) spectrophotometer and a Systronics 331 pH-meter were used. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade or of the best available quality. Double-distilled demineralized water was used throughout. A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of carbofuran (Rallis India) was prepared in ethanol and a working standard solution (10 µg ml⁻¹) was prepared by appropriate dilution with water. Solutions of 1.5 M NaOH in water, 0.5% *p*-anisidine (Merck) in ethanol, and 0.1% *N*-chlorosuccinimide (Merck) in water were prepared. Catalytic mixture was prepared by dissolving sodium nitroprusside (0.025 g) and manganese dioxide (0.025 g) in water (100 ml).

Procedure : To an aliquot of the standard solution containing 2.5–25 µg of carbofuran 1.5 M NaOH (2 ml) solution was added and kept for 15 min for complete hydrolysis. Then solutions of *p*-anisidine (0.5 ml), *N*-chlorosuccinimide (1 ml) and the catalytic mixture (0.5 ml) were added to it and the solution was kept for 15 min at room temperature for complete color development. The greenish blue dye was obtained. The solution was made up to 25 ml with water and its absorbance was measured at 660 nm against demineralized water since reagent blank had negligible absorbance at this wavelength.

Application : The proposed method was satisfactorily

applied to the determination of carbofuran in polluted water, soil, foliages and biological (blood and urine) samples. The results obtained were in good agreement with the reported method⁶. To check recoveries known amount of carbofuran was added to the samples and then determined by both the proposed and the reported method, and the recoveries are as follows : water (96.60–98.30%), soil (96.50–97.20%), foliage (96.00–97.06%), blood (95.6–96.9%) and urine (95.0–95.6%).

TABLE 1—COMPARISON WITH OTHER REPORTED METHODS

Reagent	λ_{\max} nm	Beer's law detection limit ppm	Remarks
4-Aminoantipyrine ^a	475	0.5–20	Reagent unstable, high blank problem
Sulphanilic acid ^b	470	1.0–40	Poor sensitivity
4-Aminobenzoic acid ^c	490	0.4–12	Less selective, less sensitive
Conc. nitric acid ^d	345	2–30	Reagent corrosive, less sensitive
Vanillin phosphoric acid ^e	550	1.0–10	Reagent corrosive, poor sensitivity
Present method	660	0.1–1.0	Highly sensitive and selective, the dye remains stable for 10 h

^aRef. 2, ^bRef. 6, ^cRef. 3, ^dRef. 5, ^eRef. 4.

Carbofuran was extracted from different samples using chloroform. The extraction efficiency of chloroform was found to be 100% as also reported in other method^{5,6}.

Agricultural waste water samples (10 ml) were extracted with chloroform (2 × 10 ml). The chloroform extract was then evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in 50% ethanol (25 ml). Suitable aliquot was analyzed as described above. Soil and

foliage samples (10 g) were treated and analyzed as above. The presence of carbofuran has been reported in blood and urine samples⁷. Synthetic samples were prepared by adding known amounts of working standard solution of carbofuran to blood and urine samples. These samples were deproteinized with trichloroacetic acid⁸, extracted with chloroform (2 × 5 ml) and analyzed as above.

The proposed method provides a simple sensitive technique for the microdetermination of carbofuran. The method has been compared with other reported spectrophotometric methods and found to be superior (Table 1). The method is free from the interference of a large number of foreign species and applicable in the determination of carbofuran in soil, water, foliages and biological samples.

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